

Industry Type and Audit Quality of Listed non Financial Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of industry type on audit quality among listed non-financial firms in Nigeria. Drawing on an *ex-post facto* research design, data were analyzed for a purposive sample of 75 firms over a ten-year period (2014–2023). Audit quality was proxied by audit firm size, auditor's opinion, and audit tenure, with attention to variations across industry categories. The results indicated that while a significant relationship does not exist between industry type and audit firm size and tenure, it exhibited a significant negative association with audit opinion. Overall, the models explain very little variation in the audit quality measures, as reflected by the low R-squared values across all dependent variables. These results suggest that while industry type may influence the nature of audit opinions, it does not substantially affect the selection of audit firm or the tenure of audit engagements. Given these results, it was recommended amongst others that regulators and professional bodies should develop clearer, sector-tailored audit guidelines to ensure that auditors apply consistent judgment across different industries, especially since industry type influences audit opinions.

Keywords: Audit Quality, Industry Type, Audit Firm Size, Auditor's Opinion, Audit Tenure, Financial Reporting

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Audit quality is widely recognized as a cornerstone of credible financial reporting, serving as a safeguard for the integrity, reliability, and transparency of information disseminated to stakeholders. High audit quality not only enhances the credibility of financial statements but also mitigates information asymmetry between managers and investors, thereby promoting the long-term strategic success and survival of organizations (Soepriyanto, Krisky, Indra & Zudana, 2020; Eshleman & Guo, 2020). According to the International Auditing and Assurance Standards Board (IAASB), auditors maintain audit quality by adhering to rigorous professional standards, exercising independence and professional scepticism, and collaborating effectively with relevant stakeholders (El-Dyasty & Elamer, 2020; Oyedokun, Famuyiwa, Dopemu, & Kujore, 2023).

Despite the global consensus on its importance, it is believed that the level of audit quality may not be uniform across industries. Variations in firm size, operational complexity, and regulatory environments often shape audit practices and outcomes in distinctive ways (Cao & Pham, 2021). Globally, highly regulated industries such as banking and telecommunications typically attract stringent audit scrutiny compared to less regulated sectors like agriculture and retail (Buntara & Adhariani, 2019; Al-Othman, 2019). This pattern is also evident in Nigeria, where

sector-specific regulations and institutional weaknesses contribute to inconsistencies in audit quality across different industries.

The significance of these variations is underscored by persistent challenges in the Nigerian corporate environment, including earnings management, fraud, and weak enforcement of standards, which have at times eroded the credibility of financial reports (Alhadab, 2018; AL-Qatamin & Salleh, 2020; Amahalu & Obi, 2020). While regulatory reforms have been introduced, empirical evidence on the extent to which industry-specific factors influence audit quality remains limited, especially within the context of emerging markets such as Nigeria (Dewi, Suhendro & Siddi, 2020). Understanding how industry characteristics interact with audit mechanisms is essential for improving audit practices, strengthening financial reporting, and fostering investor confidence (Tiamiyu & Oyedokun, 2019; Ogoun & Perelayefa, 2020; Fathi & Rashed, 2021).

Scholars have highlighted that operational complexity, regulatory intensity, and market conditions uniquely shape audit effectiveness across industries (Mesbah & Ramadan, 2022). While more regulated sectors may benefit from stringent oversight, less regulated industries often face resource and monitoring gaps that weaken audit outcomes. Moreover, audit firm attributes such as auditor size, tenure, and experience may possibly interact with these industry-specific conditions to influence audit quality in ways not yet fully understood (Monye-Emina & Jeroh, 2022). This underscores a critical gap in the literature, as the interplay between industry type and audit quality in Nigeria has not been sufficiently explored.

Addressing this gap is important for both theory and practice. Theoretically, it extends the understanding of how institutional and industry-level dynamics affect audit outcomes. Practically, it provides insights for regulators and policymakers on how to tailor oversight mechanisms to the distinct realities of different sectors, thereby promoting transparency, accountability, and trust in Nigeria's capital markets.

Anchored on these observations, the present study investigates whether industry type significantly influences audit quality among listed firms in Nigeria. Accordingly, the following null hypothesis was formulated and tested at 5% significance level:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between industry type and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Industry Type and Audit Quality

Industry type has been shown to significantly influence the quality of audits, given the sector-specific operational realities, regulatory intensity, and reporting demands. Highly regulated industries such as banking, insurance, and telecommunications require auditors with specialized technical expertise to address complex risks related to financial instruments, liquidity management, and compliance with stringent oversight mechanisms. Conversely, less regulated sectors, such as retail and agriculture, often emphasize operational audits (e.g.,

inventory management and supply chain efficiency), where audit quality hinges on the auditor's ability to detect managerial biases and guard against aggressive accounting practices (Yakubu & Oyedokun, 2021; Ofoegbu & Ndubuisi, 2024).

The complexity of an industry also shapes audit demands. Multinational and large firms in sectors such as technology or oil and gas face intricate financial reporting challenges requiring comprehensive and resource-intensive audits. In contrast, smaller firms may primarily undergo compliance-oriented checks. Fast-paced industries characterized by heightened competition and innovation, such as technology, further increase the risk of financial misreporting, thereby necessitating auditors who possess industry-specific knowledge and adaptability. Thus, audit quality depends not only on auditor independence and technical competence but also on sectoral dynamics, underscoring the need for industry-aware approaches to auditing in emerging markets like Nigeria (Oyedokun, Yunusa, & Adeyemo, 2018; Uthman, Salami & Ajape, 2022).

2.1.2 Measures of Audit Quality

Audit Firm Size

Audit firm size remains a widely employed proxy for audit quality, reflecting differences in expertise, professional competence, and resource endowments. Larger audit firms, particularly the Big Four, are frequently associated with superior audit outcomes, owing to their rigorous procedures, international reputations, and ability to attract highly skilled personnel (Abdulkarim & Omowumi, 2025; Ugwu, 2020; Wati, 2020). Nigerian evidence also supports this positive association, with larger audit firms more likely to enhance financial reporting credibility, especially when supported by effective audit committees (Abdulkarim & Omowumi, 2025).

Nevertheless, the literature also documents a more nuanced picture. Some studies reveal that smaller firms, particularly those affiliated with professional networks, can provide audit services of comparable quality (Shakhatreh, Alsmadi & Alkhataybeh, 2020; Ojo, Oyedokun & Fodio, 2020). Concerns remain regarding independence and potential conflicts of interest, especially when auditors provide non-audit services (Indarti & Widiatmoko, 2021; Imegi & Oladufire, 2018). Hence, while audit firm size is an important indicator, its effect is contingent upon the interplay of auditor independence, regulatory oversight, and sector-specific audit demands.

Auditors' Opinion

The auditor's opinion represents one of the most visible and consequential indicators of audit quality, as it reflects the external auditor's professional judgment regarding the fairness and credibility of financial statements. In Nigeria, an unqualified (clean) opinion is often equated with strong audit quality, while qualified, adverse, or disclaimer opinions raise concerns about governance, internal controls, and reporting integrity (Chadegani, Mohamed & Jari, 2011). Given the information asymmetry in emerging markets, stakeholders—including regulators, investors, and analysts, rely heavily on these opinions as signals of financial health and transparency (Asthana, Khurana & Raman, 2019; Oyedokun, Ojo, & Ugoh, 2020).

The credibility of audit opinions is shaped by auditor independence, firm size, tenure, and adherence to international auditing standards. Larger firms, particularly the Big Four, are generally perceived as issuing more reliable opinions (Yusuf & Danlami, 2024). However, long-term auditor–client relationships can compromise independence and reduce the informativeness of opinions. To address these risks, regulatory bodies such as the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) require detailed disclosures, including Key Audit Matters (KAMs), to enhance transparency and strengthen stakeholder confidence. Importantly, the market’s reaction to audit opinions varies across industries: highly regulated sectors like oil and gas or financial services often attract heightened scrutiny, with deviations from clean opinions resulting in more severe consequences (Khasharmeh, 2015).

Audit Tenure

Audit tenure, defined as the length of time an auditor or audit firm continuously serves a client, is another critical determinant of audit quality. Proponents argue that longer tenures allow auditors to develop a deeper understanding of a client’s operations, thereby improving audit effectiveness. Critics, however, contend that extended auditor–client relationships may impair objectivity and reduce professional skepticism, ultimately undermining audit quality (Dauda, Ojo, Oyedokun, & Ajayi-Owoeye, 2018; Yayangida, Ahmed, Nyor & Yahaya, 2023). Empirical evidence on the relationship remains mixed, with both very short and excessively long tenures shown to compromise audit effectiveness.

In Nigeria, where independence concerns are prevalent, regulatory guidelines advocate periodic auditor rotation in line with international best practices. Industry-specific considerations further complicate the tenure–quality relationship. For example, in technically demanding sectors such as oil and gas, longer auditor tenures may be necessary for auditors to acquire sufficient domain expertise (Asthana, Khurana & Raman, 2019). Effective audit committees can mitigate the risks of long tenure by monitoring auditor independence and performance (Khasharmeh, 2015). Market perceptions also remain nuanced: while prolonged relationships may raise suspicion of compromised independence, frequent changes in auditors can signal instability or strategic avoidance of scrutiny. Achieving an optimal balance between familiarity and independence remains essential to sustaining audit quality in Nigeria.

2.1.3 Conceptual Model

The study tends to ascertain the effects of industry type on audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria. Given the review of literature, the following conceptual model was proposed by the researcher as shown in figure 1:

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of the Study

Source: Researchers’ design, 2025

2.2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study on industry type and the quality of audit was anchored on the stakeholder theory which is discussed in the following section.

2.2.1 Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory provides a valuable lens for examining audit quality and financial reporting practices, emphasizing that organizations operate within a network of relationships involving employees, shareholders, creditors, regulators, customers, and wider societal actors, such as environmental and advocacy groups. Firms are therefore not solely accountable to shareholders but are bound by broader social contracts that create legitimate obligations to provide transparent, accurate, and decision-useful information to diverse stakeholder groups (Corporate Governance Literature, 2025).

In the Nigerian context, particularly among listed non-financial firms, stakeholder pressures are a critical determinant of reporting quality. The demand for credible financial disclosures and enhanced transparency arises from the diverse expectations of stakeholders, whose influence may either strengthen accountability or create tensions that challenge reporting integrity. Such pressures extend beyond financial reporting into the domain of integrated reporting, where stakeholders increasingly expect disclosures that combine financial and non-financial dimensions to reflect a firm's broader value creation (Roohanifar, Kuivalainen & Pereira, 2025).

Empirical evidence suggests that firms responsive to stakeholder interests are more likely to foster integrated thinking, improve audit quality, and reinforce investor confidence. Conversely, neglecting stakeholder concerns risks eroding legitimacy, diminishing trust, and exposing firms to reputational and regulatory challenges. Within Nigeria's corporate landscape, where regulatory enforcement remains uneven and industry conditions vary widely, effective stakeholder engagement is thus essential for aligning corporate objectives with external expectations. This makes Stakeholder Theory particularly relevant for understanding how industry type and external pressures interact to shape audit practices, reporting standards, and overall market integrity.

2.3 Empirical Review

Amahalu and Obi (2020) investigated the effect of audit quality on the financial performance of Nigerian listed conglomerates using secondary data from 2010 to 2019. The study focused on audit committee characteristics in particular, size, independence, and financial expertise and their relationship with return on assets (ROA) for six sampled conglomerates. Using Pearson correlation and panel least square regression analysis, the findings indicated that all three audit committee attributes had a significant positive impact on ROA at the 5% significance level. The study recommended strict adherence to the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA), which mandates balanced audit committee representation between shareholders and directors, to enhance corporate financial performance through improved audit quality.

Mesbah and Ramadan (2022) investigated the impact of audit quality measured by audit firm size, tenure, and fees on financial reporting quality, represented by accounting conservatism

and earnings management. Using secondary data from 152 Egyptian non-financial firms between 2016 and 2020, they found that audit firm size and fees positively correlate with financial reporting quality, indicating greater trust in reports audited by Big 4 firms. However, audit firm tenure showed a negative correlation with reporting quality, suggesting that extended tenure may impair audit effectiveness. The study implies that financial statement users may rely more on audits conducted by larger firms with higher fees, and it recommends that regulatory bodies limit audit firm tenure to no more than three years to preserve high financial reporting quality. These findings highlight the importance of audit firm characteristics in influencing the integrity and reliability of financial reports, shaping standard-setting policies to enhance audit practices in emerging markets.

Oyebamiji (2022) examined the impact of audit tenure on the financial reporting quality of Nigerian Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) using secondary data from 13 actively traded banks on the Nigerian Stock Exchange over an 11-year period (2008-2018). The study employed a purposive sampling technique with data drawn from audited financial statements and analyzed using the Random Effect method. Results revealed a significant positive relationship between audit tenure and financial reporting quality, supporting the learning effect theory that longer audit engagements improve auditors' understanding and, consequently, the reliability of financial statements. Additionally, financial condition negatively correlated with reporting quality.

In a related study, Ozegbe and Jeroh (2022) investigated audit quality characteristics as predictors of financial performance for Nigerian listed firms, using data from 2011 to 2020. They found that while audit tenure and audit firm size had positive but statistically insignificant relationships with firm performance measured by Return on Assets (ROA), auditor independence significantly negatively impacted ROA. Statutory audit services alone showed a significant positive effect on performance. The study recommended that regulatory bodies like the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria develop policies to monitor auditor tenure and ensure compliance with financial reporting regulations to maintain audit quality and enhance firm performance.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

In line with the approach adopted by prior studies (Igben & Jeroh, 2024; Obiora & Jeroh, 2024), this study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design, which is ideal for analyzing relationships and effects of variables that have already occurred without researcher manipulation. The design allows investigation into how industry type affects audit quality by examining historical data from publicly quoted Nigerian firms over ten years (2014-2023). The study's population consist of 102 non-financial firms listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group as of December 31, 2023. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 75 firms that were in operation throughout the period with accessible annual reports to ensure consistent and reliable data. Analysis of data and test of the study's hypothesis were based on the statistical model developed and presented thus:

firm size) recorded a mean of 0.575 indicating about 57.5% of firms are audited by larger firms; AUDO (audit opinion) recorded a low mean value of approximately 0.033 reflecting the rarity of qualified opinions; whereas, ATENURE (audit tenure) had a mean of about 0.767 indicating that most firms have relatively long auditor engagements. These statistics provide insights into the distribution and central tendencies of variables that influence audit quality analysis.

4.1.2 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis examines the relationships between different variables to determine the strength and direction of their associations.

Table 4.2 Result of Correlation Analysis

<i>Variable</i>	<i>INDT</i>	<i>AFSIZE</i>	<i>AUDO</i>	<i>ATENURE</i>
<i>INDT</i>	1.0000			
<i>AFSIZE</i>	0.0152	1.0000		
<i>AUDO</i>	-0.0876	0.0392	1.0000	
<i>ATENURE</i>	-0.0405	0.0490	-0.0555	1.0000

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025.

Table 4.2 presents the correlation coefficients for the variables in the study: industry type (INDT), audit firm size (AFSIZE), audit opinion (AUDO), and audit tenure (ATENURE). The correlations are generally weak, with industry type showing a negligible positive relationship with audit firm size (0.0152), and weak negative relationships with audit opinion (-0.0876) and audit tenure (-0.0405). Audit firm size has a small positive correlation with audit opinion (0.0392) and audit tenure (0.0490). Audit opinion and audit tenure exhibit a slight negative association (-0.0555). These results suggest limited linear associations among the study variables concerning audit quality indicators since none of the recorded coefficients close to, or above the threshold of 0.8 (see Odjaremu & Jeroh, 2019; Jeroh, 2020; Ukolobi & Jeroh, 2020; Ogieh & Jeroh, 2022; Izukwe & Jeroh, 2022; Sinebe & Jeroh, 2023).

4.1.3 Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test identifies multicollinearity in regression analysis by measuring how much the variance of a regression coefficient is inflated due to the correlation between predictors.

Table 4.3 Result of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) Test

<i>Variable</i>	<i>VIF</i>	<i>1/VIF</i>
<i>ATENURE</i>	1.01	0.994305
<i>AUDO</i>	1.00	0.995165
<i>AFSIZE</i>	1.00	0.995843
Mean VIF	1.00	

Source: Researcher's Computation, 2025.

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test measures multicollinearity in regression analysis by assessing how much the variance of regression coefficients is inflated due to correlations among predictor variables. In this study, the VIF values for audit tenure (1.01), audit opinion (1.00), and audit firm size (1.00) are all close to 1, with a mean VIF of 1.00, indicating no significant multicollinearity among these independent variables. This suggests that the

regression results are reliable and not distorted by excessive correlations between predictors (see Jeroh, 2016; Ezinando & Jeroh, 2017; Jeroh, 2018; Jeroh & Efeyunmi, 2022).

4.2 Test of Hypotheses

H₀: There is no significant relationship between industry type and audit quality of listed firms in Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Results of Model I and Test of Hypothesis I (INDT and AQUA)

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Symbol</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Std. Err.</i>	<i>t-Statistics</i>	<i>P>(t)</i>
Audit Firm Size	AFSIZE				
Industry Type	INDT	0.0034011	0.0073119	0.49	0.642
Constant		0.5654161	0.0386816	14.62	0.000
Audit Tenure	ATENURE				
Industry Type	INDT	-0.0069425	0.0062519	-1.11	0.267
Constant		0.8004909	0.0330741	24.20	0.000
Audit Opinion	AUDO				
Industry Type	INDT	-0.0063552	0.0026507	-2.40	0.017
Constant		0.0630756	0.0140228	4.50	0.000
	OBS	RMSE	R-sq	F	P
AFSIZE	750	0.4939282	0.0003	0.2163646	0.6420
ATENURE	750	0.422325	0.0016	1.233126	0.2672
AUDO	750	0.1790586	0.0076	5.748255	0.0167

Source: Researcher's Computation via STATA 13.0 * significant at 1% level; ** at 5% level

The multivariate regression output presents results indicating how industry type (represented by the variable "INDT") relates to three audit quality measures: audit firm size (AFSIZE), audit tenure (ATENURE), and audit opinion (AUDO). The regressions use 750 observations and consider both the direct effects of industry type and overall model fit.

For audit firm size (AFSIZE), the coefficient for industry type is very small (0.0034) and not statistically significant ($p = 0.642$), indicating no meaningful relationship between industry type and the size of the audit firm. Other model statistics, such as the low R-squared value (0.0003), further confirm that industry type does not explain variations in audit firm size. Regarding audit tenure (ATENURE), industry type also shows no significant effect (coefficient = -0.0069, $p = 0.267$), suggesting that the length of time an auditor serves a client is not explained by the type of industry. The adjusted R-squared remains extremely low (0.0016), again implying poor explanatory power. However, for audit opinion (AUDO), the regression reveals a negative and statistically significant relationship with industry type (coefficient = -0.0064, $p = 0.017$). This suggests that, controlling for other factors, changes in industry type are associated with a slight decrease in the likelihood of receiving a certain type of audit opinion (depending on how the opinion variable is coded). The adjusted R-squared (0.0076) is still quite low, but the F-statistic (5.75, $p = 0.0167$) is significant, indicating the model as a whole is better at explaining audit opinion outcomes compared to the other audit quality proxies.

5.0 Conclusion and recommendation

The outcome of the regression analysis indicates that industry type does not have a statistically significant relationship with audit firm size or audit tenure, but it does have a small, significant negative association with audit opinion. Overall, the models explain very little variation in the audit quality measures, as reflected by the low R-squared values across all dependent variables. These results suggest that while industry type may influence the nature of audit opinions, it does not substantially affect the selection of audit firm or the tenure of audit engagements. On this note, it was recommended that:

- i. Regulators and professional bodies should develop clearer, sector-tailored audit guidelines to ensure that auditors apply consistent judgment across different industries, especially since industry type influences audit opinions.
- ii. Audit firms should invest in continuous professional training focused on industry-specific risks and reporting complexities to improve the quality of audit judgments.
- iii. Given the low explanatory power of industry type on audit quality measures (audit firm size and tenure), regulators should broaden audit quality monitoring to include additional determinants such as auditor expertise, client complexity, and internal control systems.
- iv. Organizations should avoid relying solely on industry factors when selecting audit firms and instead consider broader audit quality indicators (e.g., specialization, independence, competence).

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